

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING CHILDREN'S VISUAL ARTS ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article focuses on the organization of a core group of games unique to the preschool organization and effective learning through the use of these games through various methods.

Key words: Use of nature, exercises, subject matter, use of images; teaching methods, use of fiction, images.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена организации основной группы игр, уникальных для дошкольной организации, и эффективному обучению посредством использования этих игр различными методами.

Ключевые слова: Использование природы, упражнения, предмет, использование изображений; методы обучения, использование художественной литературы, изображений.

Introduction. In the organization of preschool education a great place is occupied by independent work of children, only this independent work does not include solving complex tasks of children, because such complex tasks require a long time. Other methods are difficult for preschoolers, as almost all of them are connected with problem solving.

Game methods form the main group unique to preschool organization and these games can be used in various methods. Demonstration method and training methods. The observation method forms the general basis of the visual training system. Because it serves as an important factor in exploring, cognizing and reflecting the environment. The creative abilities of children depend on how well children have developed the ability to observe, communicate with the surrounding world, distinguish between the ordinary and the unusual. But the observation itself does not allow to fully describe what is seen. It is necessary to teach children important techniques of depiction, ways of using various visual materials. Methods of demonstration and teaching methods include the use of nature, reproductions of pictures, samples, other demonstration means, consideration of separate objects, demonstration of visual techniques by the

teacher, display of children's works at the end of the lesson, including their evaluation.

Use of Nature. The use of nature in fine arts means the depiction of an object or scene on the basis of observation. When working with nature, the appearance of an object is depicted from a certain point of view, taking into account the position of the nature in relation to the eyes of the person drawing. Based on this, the pictorial feature helps to develop a special perception during learning. The main thing here is the perception of the viewer, the object depicted on the plane (picture, applique) is perceived only from one side; children should be able to turn the nature and analyze the size and shape in different ways when making products from clay and construction. Let's consider some features of using nature in work with preschool children. Nature facilitates the work of memory, because the visual process is combined with perception and helps to correctly understand and convey the shape, structure, color of the object. Regardless of the abilities of preschoolers 4-5 years old, compared to the work of a schoolboy or artist with nature, there is a peculiar difference in the way children analyze the depicted object and work with this nature. For children of preschool age, the object of simple shape, clear drawing and clearly divided into parts is chosen as a nature. The nature should be arranged so that all children get this nature from the same character. For example, children draw a car from the side and a doll from the front and cannot convey size. If there are a large number of children in the group, 2-3 identical objects are placed on each child so that they look the same. The educator examines nature in detail with the children, facilitating the process of analysis and guiding it with his words and actions. This process requires a certain culture of perception, developed analytical thinking. Such skills begin to develop in children at the age of 5-6. At this age, children try to compare what is described with nature. For example, when describing the branches of a spruce tree in nature in a large group, children place the branch in space (vertically or obliquely) and draw the number and size of branches on the branch on the left and right sides, in dark or light color. color. color. Live birds and animals cannot be used as nature.

Their movements and sounds distract children from drawing, prevent children from perceiving the object in the right position and concentrating their attention on one point. Review items at the beginning of the lesson. In small and medium-sized groups, special objects are often shown at the beginning of instruction. Balls, ribbons, spatulas are shown to the children to focus their attention on the task at hand and to enliven their imagination. For the remainder

of the lesson, children draw based on their imagination. They cannot compare their images with the objects they see, nor do they return to their perception of those objects. It will be possible to review a topic even in a large group. For example, before drawing a picture or making an object on the theme of the fairy tale “Three Bears”, the educator should offer the children to look at a toy bear, identify the main features of the shape of the object and proportions. Some parts offers to observe the change. Children choose which episode of the fairy tale to draw, and depict the bear in a suitable pose in relation to this episode.

Use of exemplar. The use of examples is more of a teaching method. As an exemplary method of teaching are used such types of visual activities, the purpose of which is not to strengthen the impression of the perception of the surrounding, but to develop some specific moments of this activity. It is most often used in decorative and constructive (appliqué) works. Learning to create a decorative drawing is the development of artistic taste. Children should be shown beautiful objects to enhance their overall aesthetic taste. For example, carpets, vases, embroidery, etc. In decorative drawing classes, children not only reflect the objects they have seen and redraw patterns on them, but also learn to reflect patterns and draw independently, combining bright colors and shapes. Therefore, at the initial stage, children draw elements of the pattern according to the pattern, and then change the position and color of the elements. After children have mastered a certain skill, children can be shown several different patterns. In some activities, the teacher sets a pattern and children look at, familiarize themselves with, and work independently without the teacher's guidance. When drawing an object or making an object, the model is not for copying, but for determining the idea of the object to be depicted. How to use pictures. Pictures mainly serve to define children's perception of the world around them and explain their methods and tools of depiction. Studies by educators and psychologists show that children of 2 years old understand a picture as a representation of an object. But understanding the connection between the characters in the picture, that is, actions, occurs later, at 4-5 years old. For example, a child of 2 years old says that the animals in the picture “stand”, and a child of 4-5 years old says that they “talk”, “walk”, “go” and so on. Children's observations are often short-term (e.g., observing animals in urban settings). Therefore, the use of pictures helps to recapture and identify the main characteristic of the next image. Pictures are necessary in the following situations: they serve to familiarize with some ways of depicting the desired object when it is not at hand, or if it is not at hand, it is in the airplane. For

example, a teacher shows a picture to explain a distant object to children. In real life, if children perceive that distant objects are on the same line, the educator shows and explains in the picture that they are far away, from the age of 6 years the picture can be used for this purpose. Looking at the picture, the child should draw the earth not in one line, but a wide area of land, distant objects are higher, near objects are lower, and the paper is tied. realizes that he will be placed on the edge. If a picture is left in front of the children during the lesson, the children will learn to copy without even realizing it. The educational process in the preschool educational institution determines the size of the visual skills and competencies that children should master. Defines the size of a narrow range of skills. A child with a limited range of skills can describe a variety of subjects. For example, to draw a house, one must be able to draw a rectangle, that is, be able to connect lines at right angles. These drawing techniques are used to draw cars, trains, and other rectangular objects. The teacher's demonstration of pictorial media is a hands-on demonstration method that teaches children to consciously draw the desired shape based on concrete experience. There are 2 types of instructions: 1) instruction by gestures; 2) showing by drawing. In both types, instruction is given through verbal explanation. The location of the object on the paper is explained by gesture. The movement of the hand or pen on the paper is enough even for children 3-4 years old. Through gestures the child memorizes the basic shape of a complex object or its separate parts. At the end of the lesson, he participates in the evaluation of the pictures and chooses good pictures himself. It is also carried out during visualization activities with children of 6 years old. But compared to a small group these games are much less. For example, on a walk, children take pictures with their "cameras" of the neighborhood: trees, birds, animals, etc.

When they come to the kindergarten, they "scan and print" the pictures taken, that is, they write on paper what they see. When a teacher uses play, he or she should not turn all learning into play. Because this can divert children's attention from the task to the system of acquiring skills and qualifications. The instructions of the teacher can be directed to the whole group of children or to individual children. Instructions for the whole group will be given at the beginning of the training. They should be short, concise and clear. In medium and large groups, the educator asks the child about the sequence of the task and what methods should be used to find out how much the children have mastered the task. Such repeated questions help them to understand better. After the explanation and demonstration in the small group, the teacher reminds the

children again where to start. In the large group, the children are asked to think about what to draw or make, what is the main part of it, how to place the objects. After the children start working, the teacher should not start giving instructions to each child, but should ask the children who cannot start working what is unclear, such children are once again explained.

In conclusion, it is necessary to say that it is not necessary to instruct all children. Teaching is necessary for hesitant, shy, self-confident children. The teacher does not always have to anticipate the difficulties that arise. If the tutor sees that some children can do it on their own, the tutor cannot refuse the instruction. The main thing is that the child should be able to face the problem and find a way to solve it. Instructions should be different for all children. Some children are instructed in a praiseworthy tone, while confident children are more demanding. The teacher's instructions should not be direct, in the form of orders. He should encourage the child to think. When showing the child's mistake, it is necessary to draw attention to the fact that the meaning of the image changes.

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